

Letter to Editor

Dermatosurgical Problems: Cerebriform Intradermal Melanocytic Nevus Developing from a Giant Congenital Scalp Nevus

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How to cite this article: Tchernev G, Tchernev KG Jr, Kordeva S. Dermatosurgical Problems: Cerebriform Intradermal Melanocytic Nevus Developing from a Giant Congenital Scalp Nevus. *Eur J Med Health Res*, 2025;3(6):36-8.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2025.3(6).06

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The Letter

Authors report a 8-year-old boy who presented to the dermatology department with progressive hair loss and intense itching involving the right temporal region, the right half of the scalp vertex, and the right half of the frontal region. He was born with a giant congenital scalp nevus classified as large (22cm x 28cm), without hypertrichosis or satellite lesions (figs. 1a-1b). After eight years, the lesion demonstrated notable changes, including loss of pigmentation, progressive enlargement alongside intense pruritus and discomfort (fig. 1c). Histopathological examination confirmed the diagnosis of a cerebriform (congenital) intradermal melanocytic nevus. Differential diagnoses included nevus sebaceous, which is known also to undergo malignant transformation.

Given the risk of degeneration or malignant transformation into melanoma, surgical excision with consideration of reconstructive approaches - due to the expected large primary defect - was recommended.

The occurrence of cutaneous melanomas based on congenital giant melanocytic nevi is a fact that should not be overlooked [1]. Moreover, this transformation could occur even in the early childhood years [2].

The psychosocial aspect of this problem is no less serious than the morphological or organic one [3,4]. On the one hand, young patients may suffer from

depression, while at the same time being often avoided by their contemporaries [3].

During certain stages of the treatment itself (application of tissue expanders to the skin), this problem may be exacerbated [4].

It is precisely these arguments that should necessitate a serious early rethinking of the therapeutic strategy.

The scalp area is exposed to permanent or intense solar radiation, which contributes to the aggravation of the overall problem [5]. According to the currently accepted understanding of skin cancers pathogenesis and cutaneous melanoma in particular, photocarcinogenesis is and remains the key mechanism that can induce, assist, or influence the transition of nevi to melanoma through the induction of certain mutations in the melanocytes [6].

Therapeutic algorithms for those affected by such type of melanocytic lesions include their rapid and accurate reassessment, their presentation to the parents of young patients in a specific form, with particular emphasis on the urgency of the problem [7,8].

Parents' decisions should be made quickly precisely because melanocytes migrate deep into the skin during the first weeks of life of "young patients" [9], meaning that the morphology of congenital giant melanocytic nevi can sometimes change rapidly, and these changes rarely lead to regression or involution [10-12].

Therapeutic treatment or elimination of risky lesions such as giant melanocytic lesions/cerebral intradermal nevi/in the scalp area involves the application of various types of reconstructive plastic surgery in combination with tissue expanders, dermabrasion, and/or curettage [13-14].

The purpose of expanders, for example, is to gain a larger amount of skin that can be moved and adapted in the direction desired by clinicians. A number of dermatosurgical centers specialize in this area and show relatively good long-term results.

Unfortunately, not all parents perceive these aggressive approaches as the right alternative, which is why lesions can grow significantly over time and evolve into more risky ones.

A typical example of this is the cerebriform melanocytic nevus, which could arise as a result of transformation based on a previously existing congenital giant melanocytic nevus [15].

There is also evidence of cerebriform intradermal nevi of the scalp transforming into cutaneous melanoma [16,17].

The similarity between the cerebriform giant intradermal melanocytic nevus and the giant sebaceous nevus in the clinical case we describe is evident and apparent due to: 1) the loss of pigmentation of the giant melanocytic nevus over time and 2) the change in clinical morphology in the form of a cerebriform surface (see photographic material). This is also the reason for the working diagnosis of sebaceous nevus at the initial examination of the patient.

The photographs of the newborn presented by the parents during the examination were the main reason for the initial diagnosis (Figures 1a and 1b): a large congenital melanocytic nevus on the scalp, which had evolved into a cerebriform intradermal nevus (Figure 1c).

Figure 1 (a,b): A large (22cm x 28 cm) congenital melanocytic nevus located in the right temporal region, the right half of the scalp vertex, and the right half of the frontal region; (c): Transition of the giant congenital melanocytic nevus of the scalp into cerebriform scalp nevus within time duration.

The common and important feature of the two diagnoses/differential diagnoses mentioned above (sebaceous nevus/intradermal melanocytic nevus) is that the choice of future treatment regimen is similar, analogous, and focused on aggressive therapeutic methods or methods that guarantee the highest degree of success.

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